

STUDENTS SURVEY

Assessing active learning in an architectural design studio course (students version)

1. 1. What is your GPA?

Mark only one oval.

- More than 3.6
- Between 2.4 - 3.6
- Below 2.0

2. 2. In case you joined a studio course during the pandemic (COVID 19) crisis, which is a better studio setting?

Mark only one oval.

- Online Studio
- Traditional/Physical design studio
- Hybrid or blended design studio (A merge of online and traditional studio)
- Other: _____

3. 3. Regarding your **INDIVIDUAL** project experience in the interior design (1) studio course, what did you achieve from the following **learning by doing** criteria? (you can tick more than 1 box)

Check all that apply.

- Experiential learning (cafeteria visits/ observation/ site visit)
- Inquiry based learning (fixing the project problem through your proposed design)
- Collaborative learning (brainstorming with your peers)
- Design-Build programs (Building a 1-1 model by hand or in virtual rooms)

4. 4. Regarding your **COLLABORATIVE** project experience in the interior design (1) studio course, what did you achieve from the following **learning by doing** criteria? (you can tick more than 1 box)

Check all that apply.

- Experiential learning (atrium/exhibition visits and observation)
- Inquiry based learning (fixing the project problem through your proposed design)
- Collaborative learning (brainstorming with your peers)
- Design-Build programs (Building a 1-1 model by hand or in virtual rooms)

5. 5. What did the **COLLABORATIVE** project experience mainly achieve from the following points? (pick two only)

Check all that apply.

- Encouraging diverse opinions and interaction
- Encouraging collaborating with other fields (structure engineers, carpenters..etc)
- Gaining new fixation and building skills
- Other: _____

6. 6. **Potential learning** prepares students for their professional careers, which project encouraged potential learning more?

Mark only one oval.

- The individual project
- The Collaborative project (Group work)
- Both
- None of the above

7. 7. If **potential learning** was achieved based on your opinion, how was it achieved? (pick two only)

Check all that apply.

- Through gaining new business and management skills
- Through professional guidance (professors, Drs, TAs or talks)
- Through joining a competition
- Other: _____

8. 8. There're several of **technological interventions** in the design studio courses, which were the most beneficial in your interior (1) course? (pick two only)

Check all that apply.

- An up-to-date staff members
- Incorporating 3D fabrication (with various scales) into the course
- Providing access to a library of digital models
- Providing interactive virtual rooms for students
- Other: _____

9. 9. Based on the previous question, which project achieved the chosen **technological interventions**?

Mark only one oval.

- The individual project
- The collaborative project
- Both
- None of the above

10. 10. An effective teaching and learning process focuses on the design process instead of the final outcome, was this **process-focused** approach achieved?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, in the individual project only
- Yes, in the collaborative project only
- Yes, in both projects
- No, it wasn't achieved

11. 11. Based on your previous answer, which criteria emphasize your **process-focused** answer? (pick two only)

Check all that apply.

- Critical thinking was encouraged
- Collaboration and interaction were supported
- Workshops and hands-on (building 1-1 or different scales-learning by doing) experience was supported
- Other: _____

12. 12. **Reflective learning** include 4 modes/phases respectively (habitual, understanding, reflection and critical reflection) to improve the student's learning skills, which phase did you reach in design course?

Mark only one oval.

- Habitual phase (receiving new materials/data without understanding)
- Understanding phase (understanding the idea/data received by the staff as facts and theories without an actual application)
- Reflection phase (Fully understand the data and offer useful applications)
- Critical reflection (achieving all the previous points plus providing your own opinion and criticism)

13. 13. Based on your previous answer, which project achieved **reflective learning**?

Mark only one oval.

- The individual project
- The collaborative project
- Both

14. 14. Regarding your learning experience, how much are you satisfied with your **INDIVIDUAL PROJECT**?

Mark only one oval.

Absolutely Dissatisfied

1

2

3

4

5

Absolutely Satisfied

15. 15. Regarding your learning experience, how much are you satisfied with your **COLLABORATIVE PROJECT**?

Mark only one oval.

Absolutely Dissatisfied

1

2

3

4

5

Absolutely Satisfied

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